

Bluro MindSight: A Cognitive Wearable Assistant

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Abstract

This paper introduces MindSight, a wearable assistant designed to augment personal productivity and cognitive abilities. MindSight's primary function revolves around facilitating memory retention from conversations, offering users an efficient mechanism to recall crucial information and make well-informed decisions. By utilizing intelligent analysis and summarization of discussions, MindSight transforms intricate data into actionable insights, effectively converting routine conversations into strategic action plans. It also transcends conventional wearable devices by harnessing the camera functionality embedded in the device to support visual learning. This unique feature furnishes detailed explanations for diagrams and visual representations, significantly amplifying comprehension and retention rates. Particularly beneficial for grasping new concepts and deciphering complex visuals effortlessly, this capability enhances the learning experience manifold. In addition to its cognitive assistance features, MindSight seamlessly integrates web search functionality, empowering users to access information swiftly and efficiently. Employing advanced algorithms for Natural Language Processing (NLP), Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), Vision Language Models, and the Internet of Things (IoT), MindSight tailors its assistance to individual preferences and objectives. This personalized and adaptive support system ensures that users' unique needs are met, enhancing their overall experience. MindSight represents a significant advancement in wearable cognitive assistance technology, transcending the confines of traditional wearable assistants. Its user-centric design fosters transformative experiences, equipping individuals with the requisite tools to achieve their goals and unlock their full potential. By optimizing daily routines, streamlining decision-making processes, and elevating cognitive abilities, MindSight heralds a new era in wearable cognitive assistance technology.

Keywords—Wearable assistant, cognitive augmentation, Retrieval Augmented Generation, Vision Language Model, Conversational Assistance, AI Agents, Large language Models

I. INTRODUCTION

The realm of wearable technology has witnessed remarkable advancements, with the integration of AI capabilities paving the way for innovative solutions aimed at enhancing human productivity and cognitive abilities. In this paper, we present Bluro MindSight, an AI-powered wearable cognitive assistant designed to revolutionize personal productivity. MindSight seamlessly integrates cutting-edge hardware components with sophisticated software algorithms, offering users a comprehensive solution to streamline daily tasks, facilitate information retention, and augment decision-making processes.

MindSight helps users connect with support resources by recognizing their emotional states and providing them with empathetic responses. It can enhance awareness of eating habits through the monitoring of eating behaviors, while also offering guidance on safe eating levels and providing tips for fostering healthier dietary habits. MindSight can serve as an indication system for individuals who are both deaf and blind. For those who are blind, MindSight enables the identification of surroundings through auditory perception. Similarly, for those who are deaf, the display feature allows for the visualization of transcriptions, providing invaluable assistance.

II. FEATURES AND POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS

• **Transcription of Audio**

MindSight incorporates audio processing capabilities that helps in transcribing spoken language into texts. It does this by capturing nuances of speech patterns using Whisper as the transcribing model. This feature enables users to record and review spoken conversations, lectures, meetings, facilitating efficient information retention.

• **Acts as a second brain**

MindSight serves as a cognitive augmentation tool which helps users with various tasks like memory retention, decision making and problem solving, personalized recommendations and task organization.

• **Scene description using computer vision**

Utilizing computer vision technology, MindSight analyzes the user's surroundings in real-time. The camera and sensors embedded in the smart glass captures visual content and Vision Language Model is used to process it in order to generate useful information from it.

• **Multi Agents**

MindSight incorporates a multi-agent system which comprises multiple autonomous entities that work together to fulfill the user's needs and preferences. Each agent has different functionalities depending on the tasks associated with it.

Some of the potential applications of MindSight are listed below:

- By recognizing emotional states, it offers empathetic responses, thereby connecting users with support resources when needed.
- MindSight can help people with disability problems by providing navigation, and obstacle detection. It can also help them with their daily tasks.
- MindSight can give awareness about the eating habits by monitoring eating behaviors . By Providing safety eating levels it offers tips for healthier eating habits
- Users can dictate notes, memos, or ideas, which are then transcribed in real-time by the smart glass, which acts a convenient tool for capturing the spoken content more effectively.
- Individuals with memory impairments can benefit from the smart glass's ability to record and recall important information, acting as a cognitive aid to support daily activities.

III. HARDWARE

The hardware architecture of Bluro MindSight comprises several essential components, each playing a crucial role in ensuring seamless functionality. At the heart of the system lies the XIAO ESP32 Sense microcontroller, meticulously selected for its compact form factor and robust processing capabilities. With 8MB of PSRAM and a dual-core, 32-bit processor running at speeds of up to 240 MHz, the Esp32 serves as the primary controller of the wearable device, orchestrating its operations with precision.

Integrated sensors, including the oV2640 camera sensor and Digital Microphone, enhance the device's capabilities, enabling it to capture both audio and visual inputs seamlessly. The use of the oV2640 camera sensor allows the device to capture visual information to make the AI understand the environment, while the Digital Microphone, connected via I2S, facilitates audio recording.

Fig 1. Hardware Design

The display module is composed of two 0.96-inch RGB TFT displays. These displays are relayed through optics for near-eye presentation, offering users an immersive viewing experience. Furthermore, a custom 3D-printed glasses model has been designed to house the components, ensuring optimal comfort and wearability for extended usage periods.

Addressing the constraints of the XIAO ESP32 Sense, which features only one SPI pin, a strategic design approach was employed. The SD card reader and the two displays were connected utilizing a single master and multi-slave configuration. By assigning distinct Chip Select pins for each component, efficient data transmission and control were achieved within the system.

Powering the device is a rechargeable battery, providing users with the freedom of mobility. Additionally, data storage needs are seamlessly met through the integration of an SD card, offering ample space for storing captured content and user data and for logging. Touch buttons and controls have been strategically integrated into the device, allowing users to navigate menus, adjust settings, and interact with content effortlessly.

Due to constrained hardware resources within the desired form factor, the incorporation of a GSM module for internet connectivity was deemed unfeasible for this wearable device. This decision was primarily driven by concerns regarding increased radiation exposure inherent to GSM integration, particularly when situated in close proximity to the user's head. The utilization of Wi-Fi capabilities inherent to the ESP32 microcontroller was chosen as an alternative means of internet connectivity. By leveraging mobile hotspot functionality, the wearable device acts as a peripheral device, establishing a wireless connection to the internet through a user's mobile device. This strategic approach not only circumvents the limitations posed by hardware constraints but also mitigates potential health risks associated with GSM radiation exposure near the user's head. In anticipation of potential inconsistencies in user-initiated mobile hotspot activation, a fallback mechanism was integrated into the Bluro MindSight wearable device. Recognizing that users may not always have their mobile hotspot enabled, this mechanism ensures uninterrupted data transmission and connectivity. In the event that data cannot be immediately sent to the server due to lack of internet access, it is temporarily stored in the onboard SD card. Subsequently, when the device regains connectivity, the stored data is automatically retrieved and retransmitted.

to the server. This proactive approach not only addresses potential disruptions in internet connectivity but also enhances the reliability and robustness of the device's data transmission capabilities.

IV. SOFTWARE

In the software architecture of the Bluro MindSight glasses, meticulous design and implementation strategies are employed to ensure efficient utilization of resources and seamless functionality. Initially developed as a bare metal program, the limitations of sequential flow prompted the adoption of FreeRTOS, enabling concurrent execution across the two cores of the ESP32 microcontroller. Task-based organization forms the cornerstone of the software, with each feature of the glasses encapsulated within individual tasks, facilitating modularity and dependency management.

The glasses boast three primary features: Conversation Tapping, Scene Description, and Assistant Agent, each orchestrated through dedicated Real-Time Operating System (RTOS) tasks. The Audio Recorder task serves as the cornerstone of the device, tasked with capturing conversational audio via the onboard microphone interface using I2S protocol. Employing a queue-based approach, two audio buffers, each spanning 10 seconds, are maintained to facilitate continuous audio capture. Upon capturing each audio segment, it is enqueued, triggering a notification to the Audio Sender task for further processing. The Audio Sender Task, synchronized with the Audio Recorder task, retrieves audio buffers from the queue upon notification. These buffers are then processed into WAV format and transmitted to a server via HTTP client, adhering to a time-based mechanism. In cases of transmission failure, a fallback mechanism temporarily stores the audio on the SD card, ensuring data integrity. Timestamping of audio files facilitates efficient server-side storage and retrieval.

The Scene Describe Task orchestrates the capture of images using the device's camera and the simultaneous recording of user speech audio, which together constitute the user query. This amalgamation of visual and auditory input is then transmitted to a server. Upon receipt, the server transcribes the audio into textual query format. This textual query is subsequently utilized to interact with a Vision Language model, facilitating the generation of scene descriptions.

The Notification Service Task establishes a WebSocket connection with a notification provider server, handling incoming requests such as text display notifications. Messages received from the server are relayed to the near-eye displays of the glasses, presenting pertinent information to the user, including responses from the Assistant Agent or task notifications.

Finally, the Display Task centralizes all display-related operations, ensuring seamless presentation of processed information to the user.

- **Mindsight Mobile Application: Facilitating Seamless Integration and User Interaction**

The Mindsight mobile application features an intuitive and visually appealing user interface designed to provide users with easy access to various functionalities and settings. Through well-organized menus and intuitive navigation, users can effortlessly configure their preferences and interact with the system's features.

The mobile application allows users to configure and manage agents responsible for executing tasks within the Mindsight system. For instance, users can link their Gmail accounts to enable email-related tasks, such as composing and sending emails, directly from the wearable device. Through the app, users can specify settings and preferences for each agent, tailoring the system's behavior to their individual needs.

Users can customize notification settings through the mobile app, enabling them to stay informed about important updates, task completions, or system events. By providing granular control over notifications, the app ensures that users receive relevant information without being overwhelmed by unnecessary alerts. It also acts as

a bridge between the wearable device and the backend system, facilitating seamless communication and interaction. Users can initiate actions, configure settings, and view relevant information through the app, with changes reflected in real-time on the wearable device.

V. BACKEND ARCHITECTURE AND WORKFLOW

Our system leverages a hybrid approach combining monolithic and microservices architectures to manage various components and functionalities effectively.

Fig 2. Flowchart Depicting the Workflow of the Components

A. Components of the Backend Architecture

The backend architecture of Bluro MindSight comprises several interconnected components aimed at processing user inputs, facilitating seamless interaction with AI models, and executing tasks requested by the user. These components include:

- 1) **FastAPI Server:** A pivotal component built on the FastAPI framework, serving as the primary interface for communication between the wearable device and the backend system. The server accommodates both HTTP and WebSocket connections, allowing for real-time data exchange.
- 2) **Audio Transcription and Speaker Diarization Services:** Integrated with OpenAI Whisper, this service is responsible for transcribing conversational audio inputs and identifying speakers through diarization techniques. The resulting transcriptions are structured in a group chat format, enabling effective communication and interaction analysis.
- 3) **Vision Language Model (VLM):** Employed for comprehending visual scenes captured by the device camera, the VLM interprets image snapshots provided by users and generates textual descriptions. This component plays a crucial role in responding to user queries related to visual content.

- 4) **Vector Database and Embedding Functionality:** Utilizing ChromaDB, our system employs a vector database to store multimodal conversational histories and embeddings derived from both audio and visual inputs. This enables efficient retrieval and manipulation of data for various operations, including Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG).
- 5) **Agent Manager and Agents:** Facilitating task execution initiated by the Language and Vision Models, the Agent Manager coordinates interactions with specialized agents responsible for performing specific actions. These agents interface with external services such as email providers, executing tasks based on user requests.

B. Workflow of the Components

1) FastAPI Server:

Front Facing Server: The Front Facing Server, implemented using FastAPI, serves as the primary interface for communication between the Bluro MindSight wearable device and the backend system. This component facilitates the reception of various data types, including JPEG image files, WAV audio files, and text data, from the wearable device through both HTTP and WebSocket connections.

1.1) Data Types and Connection Establishments

The server is designed to accept two main types of requests from the wearable device:

- **Conversation Requests:** These requests contain 10-second WAV audio files capturing user conversations, along with timestamps. The purpose of these requests is to capture user interactions and ambient conversations, enabling the system to retain information and track user activity effectively.
- **Assistant Requests:** Assistant requests may include WAV audio, image data, or a combination of both. These requests are directed towards interaction with the Language and Vision Language Models (LLM and VLM, respectively). When an assistant request is received, the audio portion is transcribed into text and passed to the LLM for generating a response. For assistant requests involving image data, such as queries regarding visual content perceived by the user, an image snapshot captured by the wearable device's camera is included in the request. This image is analyzed by the Vision Language Model (VLM) to extract relevant information. Simultaneously, the accompanying audio query is transcribed into text. The outputs from both the VLM and audio transcription are forwarded to the LLM, which generates an appropriate response based on the combined inputs. The LLM's response is then sent back to the user in real-time via WebSocket communication, facilitating seamless interaction and feedback.

1.2) Interaction Flow and Real-time Response

Upon receiving assistant requests, the Front Facing Server orchestrates the interaction flow between the wearable device and the backend AI models. The audio data is transcribed into text, enabling natural language processing by the LLM. Simultaneously, if visual content is provided, it undergoes analysis by the VLM. The combination of textual and visual inputs allows for a comprehensive understanding of user queries and context. The generated response from the LLM is transmitted back to the user in real-time via WebSocket communication, ensuring seamless and responsive interaction between the user and the Bluro MindSight system.

2) Audio Transcription and Speaker Diarization Service

Upon receiving conversational audio input, the Audio Transcription and Speaker Diarization component employs sophisticated techniques to identify speakers and assign unique speaker IDs through diarization. This

process segments the audio stream into speaker-specific segments, enabling precise speaker identification throughout the conversation. Subsequently, the system transcribes the speech of each speaker, creating a structured representation akin to a group chat. Each transcript segment is associated with the respective speaker's unique ID, facilitating seamless tracking and analysis of individual contributions within the conversation.

Moreover, an integral component of this process is the utilization of a Language and Speaker Mapping Model (LSMM). The LSMM, often referred to as the Large Language Model (LLM), dynamically analyzes the conversational flow to map speaker IDs to their corresponding actual names. For instance, in a dialogue snippet:

User1: "Hey John."

User2: "Hey Jack! How are you?"

The LSMM discerns that User1 is referred to as "Jack" and User2 as "John." This mapping is stored in memory for subsequent conversations, ensuring accurate identification and personalized responses. Therefore, when a user addresses another participant by name, the system intelligently directs the interaction to the intended recipient, fostering a natural and intuitive communication experience.

Speaker diarization is the process of partitioning an audio stream containing human speech into single segments according to the identity of each speaker. It can beautify the clarity of an automated speech transcription via means of structuring audio streams into speaker turns.

Speaker diarization systems are broken down into smaller systems. They are:

- **Speech Recognition:** Speech Recognition focuses on enabling computers to understand and interpret human speech. Speech popularity includes changing spoken language into textual content or executing instructions primarily based totally at the identified words. This technology relies on algorithms and machine learning models to process and understand human speech in real-time.
- **Speech Segmentation:** Speech segmentation is the process of identifying the boundaries between words, syllables, or phonemes in human speech. Speech segmentation is an important step in speaker diarization because additional speech analyses are performed for each framed speech segment. Conventional segmentation strategies generally section speech the usage of a set body length for computational simplicity.
- **Clustering:** Speech clustering refers to the task of identifying unique speakers within a set of audio recordings without prior knowledge of who or how many speakers are present. Speech clustering aims to group speech segments from the same speaker together. It provides information about speaker changes in the audio, which is beneficial for speech recognition.
- **Labeling Clusters:** After growing the clusters, those clusters are then labeled, typically through the variety of speakers.
- **Transcription:** Speech transcription is the process of converting spoken language (audio) into written text. Once clusters are created and categorized appropriately, the audio can then be segmented into character clips for every speaker. Those clips are then sent through a speech recognition system that delivers the transcription.

Speaker diarization is implemented to identify who is the current speaker in the provided audio sample. Our project integrates diarization by using WhisperX. WhisperX combines Whisper ASR abilities with Voice Activity Detection (VAD) and Speaker Embedding to become aware of the speaker for every sentence withinside the transcription generated through Whisper. First, the vocals are extracted from the audio to increase

the speaker embedding accuracy and the transcription is generated using Whisper, then the timestamps are corrected and aligned using WhisperX to help minimize diarization error due to time shift. The audio is then passed into MarbleNet for VAD and segmentation to exclude silences which is then used to extract speaker embeddings to identify the speaker for each segment by TitaNet. The end result is then related to the timestamps generated via way of means of WhisperX to stumble on the speaker for every phrase primarily based totally on timestamps after which realigned the usage of punctuation fashions to compensate for minor time shifts.

3) Embedding Model and Vector Database

Output from the audio transcription and VLM components is converted into vector embeddings, facilitating efficient storage and retrieval within the ChromaDB vector database. This embedding-based representation enhances the effectiveness of RAG operations and conversation analysis.

4) Retrieval Augmented Generation

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is the technique of optimizing the output of a massive language model. Large Language Models (LLMs) are educated on substantial volumes of information and use billions of parameters to generate authentic output for responsibilities like answering questions, translating languages, and finishing sentences. RAG extends the already effective competencies of LLMs to unique domain names or an organization's inner information base, all without the want to retrain the model. It is a cost-efficient technique to enhance LLM output so it stays relevant, accurate, and beneficial in diverse contexts.

LLMs can “hallucinate”, this means that they have a tendency to expectantly generate fake responses primarily based on imagined facts. These algorithms also can offer responses which can be off-subject matter in the event that they don't have a correct solution to the user's query. Language models regularly offer well-known responses that are not tailor-made to unique contexts. This may be a main disadvantage in a customer service situation because person-to-person options are normally required to facilitate a customized patron experience.

RAG effectively bridges these gaps by providing you with a way to integrate the general knowledge base of LLMs with the ability to access specific information, such as the data present in user conversations. This method permits particularly correct and dependable responses which are not tailor-made for your organization's needs.

The basic steps included in RAG are:

- **Collecting Data:** The audio conversation is captured with the help of a microphone and it is transcribed into textual data.
- **Chunking of Data:** Data chunking is the method of breaking your records down into smaller, greater potential pieces. The conversational data after being collected is broken down into smaller chunks. Each conversational chunk is based on a specific context or topic. This also improves efficiency, since the system can quickly obtain the most relevant pieces of information instead of processing entire data.
- **Embeddings:** Each conversational chunk is converted into its vector representation. This includes transforming textual data into numerical representation which helps in further semantic analysis within the data chunks. Embeddings allows the machine to understand useful information from the data which further helps in making functionalities such as similarity search more efficient. This approach guarantees that the responses are applicable and aligned with the user's query. The embeddings are stored in ChromaDB

- **Handling User Queries:** When a user's question enters the system, it should additionally be transformed into an embedding or vector representation. The same model must be used for both the data and query embedding to ensure uniformity between the two. Once the question is transformed into an embedding, the machine compares the question embedding with the file embeddings. It identifies and retrieves the data chunks which closely resembles the query embeddings by utilizing functions like cosine similarity and Euclidean distance.
- **Response Generation:** Textual content chunks, alongside the preliminary user query, are fed into the language model. Large Language Model (LLM) will use this information to generate a coherent response to the user's questions through a chat interface.

5) LLM (Large Language Model) and Agent-based Task Execution

The LLM (Large Language Model) serves as the core intelligence hub within our Bluro MindSight system, orchestrating user query responses and conducting Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) operations. It acts as the bridge between user input and task execution, seamlessly integrating with an AI Agent Manager. The Agent Manager functions as a pivotal program designed to interface with the LLM, interpret task requests, decompose complex tasks into manageable sub-tasks, and delegate these micro-tasks to appropriate Agents.

Agents, in turn, are specialized programs responsible for executing specific actions delegated by the Agent Manager. Each Agent possesses the capability to understand task instructions, formulate action plans, and interface with relevant service providers to accomplish assigned tasks.

When a user issues a task-related query to the LLM or when the LLM detects a task-oriented query, it initiates interaction with the Agent Manager, providing comprehensive details of the task at hand. For instance, if a user query entails composing an email, the LLM communicates with the Agent Manager, furnishing relevant task information alongside pertinent context, such as the user's conversational history stored in the ChromaDB.

Upon receiving task details from the LLM, the Agent Manager undertakes the critical task of identifying the most suitable Agent from its pool of available resources. In the case of composing an email, the Agent Manager selects the Gmail Agent as the most appropriate entity to handle email-related tasks.

The chosen Agent, in this instance, the Gmail Agent, receives instructions from the Agent Manager, detailing the specific actions required to fulfill the user's request. These actions may include specifying the email subject, setting the recipient's email address, composing the email body, and ultimately sending the email.

Following the execution of the email-related actions, the Gmail Agent notifies the Agent Manager of the task's completion. Subsequently, the Agent Manager relays this information back to the LLM. Finally, the LLM communicates the status of the executed task to the user via WebSocket communication, ensuring real-time feedback and interaction.

VI. TESTING AND BENCH MARKINGS

In this section, we present benchmark results comparing the performance of two speech recognition models, which are variants of Whisper, on a computer equipped with a Nvidia GTX 1650 graphics card with 4GB VRAM. The evaluation was based on their processing times for audio snippets of varying lengths: 2 seconds, 5 seconds, 10 seconds, and 30 seconds.

- **Base Model:** The Base Model showcased a startup time of 8.34 seconds. Despite this initial delay, it excelled in subsequent audio processing tasks, demonstrating the fastest overall speeds. Notably, the model reached its optimal performance at the 10-second mark, completing the task in a remarkable 8.02 seconds.

- **Small Model:** In contrast, the Small Model exhibited a slightly longer startup time of 12.89 seconds compared to its counterpart, the Base Model. However, it delivered processing times that were nearly equivalent to the Base Model for the audio clips. Like the Base Model, the Small Model achieved its fastest processing speed at 10 seconds, accomplishing the task in 8.21 seconds.

An intriguing observation is that both models showcased quicker processing times for the 10-second audio clips compared to shorter or longer durations. Further investigation is warranted to understand the extent to which the GTX 1650 graphics card influenced these results.

VII. FUTURE SCOPES

Future iterations of MindSight are envisioned to integrate more efficient onboard processors and storage, enabling autonomous operation independent of external devices such as smartphones or tablets. This facilitates direct access to and control of the glasses' features without reliance on separate mobile applications. To enhance situational awareness, prospective versions of MindSight may integrate environmental sensors capable of detecting temperature and humidity, alongside biometric sensors for monitoring user health. Additionally, plans include the incorporation of offline language translation and information retrieval functionalities to ensure accessibility in areas with limited internet connectivity. These advancements represent a concerted effort to bolster the capabilities of MindSight, fostering greater autonomy, situational awareness, and accessibility for users across diverse settings.

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